

Functional brain activation patterns of creative metacognitive monitoring

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1. Introduction

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The neuronal underpinnings of creative ideation have been studied since the early work of Martindale and Hasenfeld (1978) and since then, neuroscientific creativity research has been continuously growing (Benedek et al., in press). By now, the vast majority of neuroscience studies on creative ideation has focused on idea generation and investigated basic cognitive functions relevant for creative performance (e.g., originality; Fink and Benedek, 2014; Pidgeon et al., 2016; Stevens and Zabelina, 2019). However, the creative ideation process might be characterized by more than idea generation, as many theoretical models also consider idea evaluation relevant for the production of creative and original ideas (Benedek and Jauk, 2018; Finke et al., 1996; Kleinmuntz et al., 2019; Lloyd-Cox et al., 2022). Following prominent dual-process models of creative ideation, creative ideas arise from the interplay of generative and evaluative phases which refer to divergent and convergent modes of thinking (Sowden et al., 2015). Although the brain activation patterns during idea evaluation have been investigated before (e.g., Ellamil et al., 2012; Mayseless et al., 2014; Rominger et al., 2020), available work has not yet considered the accuracy of this evaluative process, which may provide crucial insights into the neurophysiological correlates underlying metacognitive performance in creative ideation.

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Being able to adequately discern the creative quality of one's own ideas supports creative ideation (Guo et al., 2022; Lucas and Nordgren, 2020) and can be considered a metacognitive skill (Fleming et al., 2010; Garfinkel et al., 2015; Karwowski et al., 2020). Metacognition refers to cognition on cognition and involves monitoring and control processes to establish (complex) cognitive enterprises (Ackerman and Thompson, 2017; Efklides, 2008; Flavell, 1979; Rouault et al., 2018). The ability to properly evaluate the creative quality of own ideas and monitor creative task performance, that is knowing when generated ideas are bad or good (i.e., being aware), was termed creative metacognitive accuracy (Karwowski et

50 al., 2020) and creative metacognitive monitoring (Jia et al., 2019). These evaluative processes
51 can be considered a predominantly convergent mode of thinking that complement more
52 divergent, generative processes. Metacognitive monitoring is relevant for solving creative
53 tasks more effectively by enabling more informed decisions (e.g., whether to report, elaborate
54 or discard candidate ideas), and thus supporting metacognitive control (Finke et al., 1996; Jia
55 et al., 2019; Kaufman et al., 2016; Kaufman and Beghetto, 2013). But how well can people
56 perceive the quality of their own ideas and decide if these ideas are good or bad?

57 Silvia (2008) reported that people are well able to judge the creative value of their own
58 ideas (see also Benedek et al., 2016; Grohman et al., 2006; Kaufman et al., 2016; Rominger
59 et al., in press; Rominger et al., 2022a). Importantly, the accuracy of creative idea evaluation
60 shows meaningful interindividual (Level 2) and intraindividual (Level 1) variation. Lucas and
61 Nordgren (2020) found that the correspondence between subjective and external originality
62 ratings decreased as participants spent more time on the task. Sidi et al. (2020) found a
63 dissociation between subjective and external originality ratings after false feedbacks.
64 Furthermore, a cluster analysis presented three separate groups in terms of creative
65 metacognitive monitoring: unskilled and unaware, skilled, and unaware, and unskilled but
66 aware people (Urban and Urban, 2021). Karwowski et al. (2020) reported that intelligence
67 moderated the relation between self- and experts' assessment of creative performance.
68 Therefore, in the present study, we differentiated creative metacognitive monitoring skills
69 (Level 2) and performance (Level 1) and hypothesized that creative metacognitive
70 monitoring does not only take place when people explicitly engage in the evaluation process
71 but also during creative idea generation (Guo et al., 2022; Kleinmintz et al., 2019; Sidi et al.,
72 2020). Consequently, variations in creative metacognitive monitoring (at Level 1 and Level
73 2) should be associated with functional brain activation patterns during both creative idea
74 generation and idea evaluation. Furthermore, creative metacognitive monitoring performance

75 represents a behavioral indicator of the correspondence between the outcomes of the
76 generative and evaluative processes, which are both essential for creative ideation. But which
77 indicator of brain activation should be investigated to study the neurophysiology of creative
78 metacognitive monitoring?

79 Available EEG research has employed a broad range of creative ideation task
80 adaptations (Benedek et al., 2019; for an update see Benedek et al., in press), which showed a
81 robust association of task related power (TRP; Pfurtscheller, 1999) in the alpha band with the
82 creative ideation process (Fink and Benedek, 2014). First evidence suggests that this
83 relationship also extend to the process of idea evaluation (Rominger et al., 2018). TRP refers
84 to the change of alpha power from a phase of reference to a phase of creative idea generation
85 (or evaluation). The cognitive meaning of TRP in the alpha band depends on the location of
86 the observed power changes (as well as the specific creativity task). (1) Frontal alpha power
87 increases during divergent thinking might argue for increased executive top-down control
88 (Fink et al., 2017). (2) Increases of alpha power at (right) parietal and occipital sites were
89 interpreted as increased internal attention and inhibition of external sensory information
90 (Benedek et al., 2014; Rominger et al., 2019b, for overviews see Benedek, 2018; Fink and
91 Benedek, 2014). (3) Alpha power changes at temporal sites indicate memory and association
92 processes (Luft et al., 2018; Perchtold-Stefan et al., 2020). Taken together, relevant findings
93 point to the involvement of cognitive control, attention, and memory (associative) processes
94 during creative ideation (Benedek and Fink, 2019) and idea evaluation/elaboration (Rominger
95 et al., 2020). Due to the specificity of alpha power changes for the creative ideation process,
96 this frequency band seems a promising first target to investigate the neurophysiology for
97 creative metacognitive monitoring. Still, so far it is unknown to what extent alpha power
98 reflects cognitive versus metacognitive processes as they are typically intimately coupled in
99 creative ideation (Kleinmintz et al., 2019; Lloyd-Cox et al., 2022; Rominger et al., 2019b).

100 Although neuroscientific creativity research has not systematically investigated creative
101 metacognition to date, metacognitive accuracy has been studied in other domains by means
102 of neurophysiological methods. Fleming et al. (2010), for example, showed a significant
103 association between monitoring skills (introspection of self-performance in a visual detection
104 task) and the gray matter in the anterior prefrontal cortex. This association (independent from
105 task performance) indicates the important role of executive control processes for
106 metacognition (Fox and Christoff, 2014; Jia et al., 2019; Rouault et al., 2018).

107 In order to investigate the neurophysiological basis of creative metacognitive
108 monitoring for the very first time (to the best of our knowledge), we reanalyzed a published
109 data set (Rominger et al., 2019b), which allowed us to quantify participants' monitoring
110 accuracy of the creative process by calculating the correspondence between subjective and
111 external ratings (Schraw, 2009). In this study, participants produced single, original ideas
112 across multiple alternate uses items. We assessed EEG-brain activation during creative idea
113 generation. After idea generation, participants evaluated the creative quality of the idea (i.e.,
114 subjective ratings), which was also recorded by means of EEG. We calculated the (relative)
115 correspondence between subjective ratings and external ratings (assessed via five external
116 raters using consensual originality ratings) by subtracting subjective and external
117 performance ratings for each single creative idea as the measure of participants'
118 metacognitive monitoring performance. The aggregation across ideas (per person) served as a
119 measure of participants' metacognitive monitoring skill (e.g., Fleming et al., 2010; Garfinkel
120 et al., 2015; Rouault et al., 2018; Schraw, 2009).

121 The examination of EEG data on a trial-by-trial basis strongly asks for linear mixed-
122 effects analysis, which allows to analyze within-person effects (Level 1) and between-person
123 effects (Level 2) on the observed brain activation pattern. Based on available study findings,
124 (1) we hypothesized that individual differences in creative metacognitive monitoring (i.e.,

125 evaluation skills) might be associated with a specific brain activation pattern in the alpha
126 band reflecting a convergent mode of thinking in the creative ideation process. (2) We further
127 hypothesized that this pattern might be moderated by individual differences in creative
128 ideation performance (i.e., resulting in different brain activation patterns in people who are
129 creative but unaware vs. creative and aware; Urban and Urban, 2021). (3) We expected that
130 the activation pattern should be distinguishable during both creative idea generation (more
131 divergent mode of thinking) and idea evaluation (more convergent mode of thinking).
132 Finally, (4) this specific pattern (idea generation vs. idea evaluation) could be further
133 moderated by individual differences in creative metacognitive monitoring (i.e., evaluation
134 skills).

135 2. Methods

136 2.1 Participants

137 The total sample consisted of 102 participants. Two participants were excluded from
138 the analyses. One participant showed no variance in subjective ratings and the subjective
139 ratings of one participant were lost due to technical problems. The final sample of 100
140 participants (44 men and 56 women) had an average age of 23.07 ($SD = 3.35$; min = 18, max
141 = 33). Based on the Monte Carlo Simulation study of Arend and Schäfer (2019), who provide
142 information on power analyses of hierarchically structured data, 100 participants should be
143 sufficient to detect medium between-person and cross-level interaction effects. All
144 participants were right-handed (assessed by a standardized hand skill test; Steingrüber, 2010),
145 and were requested to refrain from alcohol for twelve hours and from coffee and other
146 stimulating beverages for two hours prior to their lab appointment, and to come to the session
147 well rested. The study was approved by the authorized ethics committee of the university of
148 Graz and written informed consent was obtained from each participant.

149 **2.2 Creative thinking task**

150 In the alternate uses task (AUT; Guilford, 1967) participants had to generate one use
151 for an everyday object that was as original as possible. We applied a single answer (best idea)
152 and self-paced AUT version, which was followed by an evaluation period asking participants
153 to rate the creative quality of their idea. This single idea approach allows the calculation of a
154 relative agreement between external and subjective ratings for each single idea (i.e., creative
155 monitoring accuracy). The AUT started with a white cross (10 s; reference period) followed
156 by a picture of a common everyday object, which indicated the beginning of the creative
157 ideation period. Participants had to press the idea button (Fink et al., 2007) as soon as they
158 decided on their best possible idea (15 s max. response time). Then, participants evaluated the
159 creative quality of their idea on a six-point Likert scale (max. 4 s response time; from 1 “low
160 quality” to 6 “very high quality”). At the end of each trial, participants briefly vocalized their
161 best idea (10 s), which was recorded and then transcribed for analysis (see Figure 1). The 16
162 AUT items (e.g., book, umbrella, brick, key) were presented in randomized order. Since this
163 paradigm did not have a forced answer design, participants generated a total of 1511 ideas
164 (94.4% response rate) and subjectively rated 1421 of their ideas (88.8%). The multi-level
165 approach is well suited to handle this small amount of missing data.

166 **2.2.1 Quantification of creative performance (Level 1) and creative potential (Level 2)**

167 Five independent judges provided the external ratings for originality of the produced
168 ideas on a four-point Likert scale ranging from “not original” (1) to “very original” (4). This
169 procedure is a common approach in creativity research (cf. Consensual Assessment
170 Technique; Amabile, 1982). The external originality ratings showed good interrater reliability
171 (ICC (2, k) = .71). All ratings were averaged across the five raters resulting in one originality
172 score for each single idea of a participant (i.e., creative performance, Level 1). Originality
173 scores were aggregated across trials for each participant for analyses of between-person

174 variance (Level 2) which provides a measure of creative potential.

175 **2.2.2 Quantification of creative metacognitive monitoring performance (Level 1) and** 176 **monitoring skill (Level 2)**

177 Creative metacognitive monitoring was assessed by the correspondence between
178 subjective and external ratings of originality at item and participant level (Fleming and Lau,
179 2014; Schraw, 2009). First, all subjective (c_i) and external (p_i) originality ratings were z-
180 transformed within each participant. Then a modification of the formula of Schraw (2009)
181 was applied to assess the correspondence between subjective and consensual ratings, as a
182 measure of relative correspondence (*Accuracy Index* = $(zc_i - zp_i)^2 * (-1)$). Higher (less
183 negative) scores indicate higher monitoring accuracy. This approach allows to estimate
184 metacognitive monitoring performance for each single trial (Level 1), as well as
185 metacognitive monitoring skills for each participant (i.e., aggregated over trials; Level 2).
186 The aggregated creative metacognitive skill showed a substantial correlation with the Pearson
187 correlation between external and subjective originality ratings within each single person of r
188 = .96 (i.e., correlation with criterion, see e.g., Garfinkel et al., 2015; Guo et al., 2022). This
189 indicates that the result of the applied formula is in high accordance with the correlation
190 approach to assess relative monitoring accuracy (Schraw, 2009; Sidi et al., 2020).

191 **2.3 EEG recordings and analysis**

192 The EEG was recorded in a separate and quiet room via 19 electrodes (10-20 system;
193 500 Hz sampling rate; Brainvision BrainAmp Research Amplifier, Brain Products™). The
194 ground electrode was located on the forehead, the reference electrode on the nose. Vertical
195 and horizontal electrooculograms were assessed with two bipolar channels for horizontal and
196 vertical eye movements. All electrode impedances were kept below 5 kΩ.

197 The g.BSanalyze software (g.tec™, Graz, Austria) was used to preprocess data by
198 removing drifts and low pass filtering of 50 Hz, to manually check the resulting signal for

199 artifacts. Similar to Rominger et al. (2019b), we calculated the band power values (μV^2) by
200 squaring the filtered EEG signals (8 - 12Hz; FFT-filter (FIR, fft function from MATLAB)
201 with a window size of 100 samples and an overlap of 99 samples). EEG-data containing
202 artifacts such as eye-blinks, eye-movements, or muscle tension were manually skipped from
203 further analyses (in the time domain). Therefore, only band power values from artifact free
204 time-intervals were averaged by means of the median. For the TRP analyses, the 8 s interval
205 from 1 s after onset of the fixation cross until 1 s before its offset served as the reference
206 interval, the period starting 500 ms after stimulus onset until 500 ms before the idea button
207 was pressed served as the activation interval 1, and 250 ms after subjective confidence rating
208 onset and 250 ms before finishing the rating served activation interval 2 (i.e., idea evaluation;
209 Figure 1). We used 250 ms for subjective ratings due to faster response times for subjective
210 ratings (max. 4 sec) in contrast to the idea button press (max. 15 sec) during creative idea
211 generation. TRP scores for each single trial were quantified for alpha power for an electrode i
212 by subtracting the log-transformed power of the reference period ($\text{Pow}_{i, \text{reference}}$) from that of
213 the activation period ($\text{Pow}_{i, \text{activation}}$; i.e., during creative idea generation and subjective rating
214 of idea quality), according to the formula: $\text{TRP}_i = (\log(\text{Pow}_{i, \text{activation}})_j) - (\log(\text{Pow}_{i, \text{reference}})_j)$.
215 Positive values indicate increases of power from the reference to the activation period
216 (Pfurtscheller and Lopes da Silva, 1999).

217 Then, valid trials were selected based on two requirements. (1) Sufficient available
218 EEG data per duration was defined with at least 750 ms for the ideation periods, at least 500
219 ms for the evaluation periods, and a minimum of 1000 ms artifact-free data for the reference
220 periods. (2) All behavioral trial data (i.e., external and subjective ratings) were available to
221 calculate metacognitive monitoring performance per trial. Considering both criteria, we
222 obtained $M = 13.04$ ($SD = 2.78$) valid trials during idea generation creative ideation and $M =$
223 12.82 ($SD = 2.64$) during idea evaluation.

224 For all statistical analyses, electrodes of relevant cortical sites per hemisphere were
 225 averaged. This procedure resulted in three separable cortical sites, which were indicated to be
 226 relevant for creative ideation (Agnoli et al., 2020; Rominger et al., 2020). We averaged the
 227 frontal areas (left: Fp1, F3, F7; right: Fp2, F4, F8), temporal/central areas (left: C3, T7; right:
 228 C4, T8), and parietal/occipital areas (left: P3, P8, O1; right: P4, P8, O2). Since we were
 229 interested in lateralized effects, all midline electrodes were excluded from further statistical
 230 analyses.

231

232 *Figure 1.* Schematic display of the AUT procedure and EEG assessment. Eight seconds
 233 out of the 10 s fixation cross period served as the reference interval (1000 ms after cross-
 234 onset until 1000 ms before cross-offset). The time from 500 ms after item onset until 500 ms
 235 before the button press served as the activation interval 1 for the generation phase. The time
 236 from 250 ms after item onset until 250 ms before the idea evaluation phase served as
 237 activation interval 2 for the evaluation phase. After the verbal response (10 s, audio
 238 recording) the next trial started.

239

240 2.4 Statistical Analysis

241 The advantages offered by linear mixed-effects analysis are the possibility to control
 242 for the random effects of participants (and random slopes of the trial number) and that it is

243 robust for a varying amount of available data per person. To investigate the behavioral
244 association between subjective and external originality ratings, we calculated a linear mixed-
245 effects model with externally rated originality as dependent variable, subjective ratings at
246 Level 1 (group mean centered) and Level 2 (grand mean centered) as continuous fixed factor,
247 and participant and trial number as random factors. We calculated the group mean centered
248 subjective rating scores by subtracting the average score of each participant from the
249 subjective rating of each single idea and the grand mean centered scores by subtracting the
250 mean of all answers of all participants from each single mean score of a participant (Finch et
251 al., 2019). To evaluate how creative metacognitive monitoring depends on subjective and
252 external ratings of ideas, we calculated a linear mixed-effects model with creative
253 metacognitive monitoring as dependent variable and subjective as well as external originality
254 ratings as fixed effects at Level 1 (group mean centered) and Level 2 (grand mean centered).

255 For neurophysiological analyses, we calculated one linear mixed-effects model to
256 investigate the impact of creative metacognitive monitoring and originality (at Level 1 and
257 Level 2) on the TRP during creative idea generation and idea evaluation. The TRP changes
258 during creative idea generation and evaluation served as dependent variable and PROCESS
259 (idea generation, idea evaluation), AREA (three regions in each hemisphere; frontal areas
260 served as reference), and HEMISPHERE (left, right) served as factorized variables. The
261 grand mean centered creative metacognitive monitoring skill (Level 2) and the group mean
262 centered monitoring performance (Level 1) as well as the grand mean originality scores
263 (Level 2; creative potential) and the group mean centered creative performance (Level 1)
264 were entered as continuous fixed effects. Participants (and trial number) served as random
265 effects. All possible combinations of these factors were entered as interaction terms into the
266 model. In case of significant interactions, simple slope analyses were conducted. A
267 significance level of $p < .05$ (two-tailed) was used for all analyses, which were calculated

268 with R (version 3.4.2; R Core Team, 2021) by applying the nlme package (Pinheiro et al.,
269 2018) and the reghelper package to calculate simple slopes (Hughes and Beiner, 2021).

270 Finally, we conducted sensitivity analyses to assess the robustness of the findings,
271 specifically in the alpha band. We calculated the very same linear mixed-effects model for
272 the adjacent frequency bands of theta (4-8Hz) and beta (12-30Hz).

273 3. Results

274 3.1 Behavioral results

275 The subjective originality ratings at Level 1 predicted the external originality ratings
276 ($t(1320) = 10.902, p < .001$), indicating that participants were able to judge the creative value
277 of their ideas during each single trial with reasonable accuracy (see Table 1). The subjective
278 ratings at Level 2 did not predict the external originality of ideas ($t(98) = 0.588, p = .558$),
279 suggesting that interindividual differences in the level of subjective ratings of own ideas do
280 not covary with interindividual differences in creative potential – that is more creative people
281 do not generally give higher ratings.

282

283 *Table 1. Multilevel model predicting externally rated originality*

Parameter	Estimate ^a (SE)	β^b	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	2.180 (0.023)		1320	96.785	<.001
LEVEL 2					
Subjective originality rating (grand mean centered)	0.017 (0.029)	.025	98	0.588	.558
LEVEL 1					
Subjective originality rating (group mean centered)	0.157 (0.014)	.256	1320	10.902	<.001
Random effects	Proportion of			<i>SD</i>	<i>r</i>

	variance		
Participant (intercept)	29.34%	0.218	
Trial number (slope)	0.81%	0.006	-0.852
Residual	69.85%	0.519	

284 N = 100 with 1421 measurements. Note. The model includes a random intercept (trial
 285 number within subject). *Df* = degrees of freedom; *SE* = standard error. ^a Estimates are
 286 unstandardized partial regression coefficients. ^b Estimates are standardized partial regression
 287 coefficients after z-standardization of all fixed continuous predictors and the criterion (i.e.,
 288 originality; for a similar procedure, see Benedek et al., 2021).

289

290 The second behavioral multi-level analysis examined trial- and person-level predictors
 291 of metacognitive monitoring (see Table 2). At Level 1, lower externally rated creativity of
 292 responses ($t(1319) = -5.236, p < .001$), but not subjective ratings, predicted higher
 293 metacognitive monitoring performance. At Level 2, higher subjective ratings ($t(97) = 2.493,$
 294 $p = .014$), but not externally rated creative potential predicted higher metacognitive
 295 monitoring skill. This pattern of findings suggests that metacognitive monitoring was higher
 296 in less creative trials as well as for people who generally gave higher subjective ratings,
 297 which is consistent with the notion that people often underestimate the creativity of
 298 responses, but less so for less creative ideas and for people showing a less negative rating
 299 bias (Benedek et al., 2016; Ceh et al., 2021).

300

301 *Table 2. Multilevel model predicting creative metacognitive monitoring*

Parameter	Estimate ^a (<i>SE</i>)	β^b	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	-1.346 (0.05)		1319	-24.854	<.001

LEVEL 2

Subjective originality rating (grand mean centered)	0.174 (0.070)	.072	97	2.493	.014
Creative potential (grand mean centered)	0.047 (0.251)	.006	97	0.188	.851
LEVEL 1					
Subjective originality rating (group mean centered)	0.065 (0.052)	.021	1319	1.240	.215
Creative performance (group mean centered)	-0.499 (0.095)	-.137	1319	-5.236	<.001
Random effects	Proportion of variance			<i>SD</i>	<i>r</i>
Participant (intercept)	26.09%			0.653	
Trial number (slope)	2.36%			0.059	-.930
Residual	71.55%			1.791	

302 N = 100 with 1421 measurements. Note. The model includes a random intercept (trial
303 number within subject). *Df* = degrees of freedom; *SE* = standard error. ^a Estimates are
304 unstandardized partial regression coefficients. ^b Estimates are standardized partial regression
305 coefficients after z-standardization of all fixed continuous predictors and the criterion (i.e.,
306 monitoring performance).

307

308 3.2 EEG results

309 All EEG results were derived from one comprehensive multi-level model (see Table 3).
310 We start by describing general findings across tasks processes (idea generation and
311 evaluation), before moving on to process-specific analyses. The null model indicated that
312 28% of total variance in TRP was due to between-person variance (Level 2). This leaves up
313 to 72% of variance in TRP due to within-person.

314

3.2.1 Brain activation during creative ideation and idea evaluation as a function of position and hemisphere

The TRP was lower at temporal/central ($b = -0.148, t(15228) = -13.814, p < .001$) and parietal/occipital areas ($b = -0.231, t(15228) = -21.525, p < .001$) compared to frontal areas. Furthermore, temporal/central sites showed higher TRP compared to parietal/occipital areas ($b = 0.083, t(15228) = 7.675, p < .001$). There was no significant TRP difference between the right and left hemisphere ($b = 0.011, t(15228) = 1.019, p = .308$). However, a significant interaction between hemisphere and temporal/central position was observed ($b = 0.053, t(15228) = 3.528, p < .001$). Post hoc simple slope-analyses indicated that right hemispheric temporal/central alpha power was higher compared to the TRP in the left hemisphere ($b = 0.045, t(8289) = 5.148, p < .001$).

3.2.2 Effects of creative metacognitive monitoring and creative potential on TRP during creative idea generation and evaluation

The interaction POSITION with creative metacognitive monitoring at Level 2 showed a significant effect for parietal/occipital sites ($b = -0.060, t(15228) = -2.976, p = .003$). Post hoc simple slope-analyses were conducted by changing reference levels for position (frontal vs. parietal/occipital) and monitoring skills at Level 2 (+1 SD). This procedure did not indicate further significant results. Furthermore, the interaction POSITION with monitoring skills (Level 2) and creative potential (Level 2) was significant ($b = -0.351, t(15228) = -3.746, p < .001$). Follow up simple slope analyses showed that metacognitive monitoring skills were negatively associated with alpha power at parietal/occipital sites in people showing higher creative potential ($b = -0.076, t(96) = -2.542, p = .013$; see Figure 2). This effect was absent in people with lower creative potential ($b = 0.005, t(96) = 0.135, p = .893$). Furthermore, an increase in alpha power at parietal/occipital sites was linked to an increase in creative potential in people with lower levels of monitoring skills ($b = 0.367, t(96) = 3.387, p = .001$). This finding was absent in people with higher monitoring skills ($b = -0.043, t(96) = -0.428, p$

341 = .669; see Figure 2). Taken together, these results suggest that creative potential
 342 significantly moderated the effects of monitoring skills on parietal/occipital TRP changes
 343 such that with increasing levels of creativity, TRP became weaker as metacognitive
 344 monitoring skills increased.

345
 346 *Figure 2.* Task-related power (TRP; and error bars) in the alpha band (8-12Hz) as a function
 347 of position, creative potential, and monitoring skills.

348
 349 The interaction between monitoring skills (Level 2) x monitoring performance (Level
 350 1) x creative potential (Level 2) was also significant ($b = 0.079, t(15228) = 2.005, p = .045$).
 351 Simple slope analyses showed increasing TRP with increasing creative potential in people
 352 with lower monitoring skills, especially when showing low metacognitive monitoring
 353 performance at Level 1 ($b = 0.254, t(96) = 2.354, p = .021$). Finally, TRP decreased with

354 monitoring skills in people with higher creative potential, especially when showing low
355 metacognitive monitoring performance at Level 1 ($b = -0.114, t(96) = -2.398, p = .018$).

356 **3.2.3 Process-specific effects of creative metacognitive monitoring skills on TRP**

357 The main effect PROCESS failed to be significant ($b = -0.021, t(15228) = -1.927, p = .054$).
358 However, the factor PROCESS showed an interaction with POSITION ($b = 0.036, t(15228) =$
359 $2.395, p = .017$). Post hoc simple slope-analyses were conducted by changing reference levels
360 for position (frontal vs. parietal/occipital). These analyses indicated that lower alpha power
361 during idea evaluation compared to idea generation at temporal/central sites ($b = -0.043,$
362 $t(7653) = -5.752, p < .001$) and at frontal sites ($b = -0.029, t(7653) = -3.958, p < .001$; see Figure
363 2-A). The interaction of PROCESS and monitoring skills (Level 2) was significant ($b = -0.054,$
364 $t(15228) = -2.636, p = .008$), which was further moderated by the factor POSITION
365 (PROCESS x POSITION x monitoring skills (Level 2), $b = 0.071, t(15228) = 2.448, p = .014$).
366 To better understand this three-way interaction, we conducted post-hoc simple slope-analyses,
367 which indicated decreased TRP at frontal ($b = -0.047, t(7648) = -4.231, p < .001$) and
368 temporal/central sites ($b = -0.055, t(7648) = -4.931, p < .001$) during idea evaluation (compared
369 to idea generation) in people with higher monitoring skills (Figure 3-B). This was also observed
370 for temporal/central sites ($b = -0.031, t(7648) = -2.788, p = .005$), when monitoring skills were
371 low, but virtually absent for frontal positions ($b = -0.006, t(7648) = -0.507, p = .612$).
372 Furthermore, metacognitive monitoring skills predicted lower TRP in frontal areas during the
373 idea evaluation process at a potentially meaningful trend level ($b = -0.057, t(98) = -1.861, p =$
374 $.066$; see Figure 3-C). Process-specific brain activation was not further moderated by neither
375 creative potential, creative performance, nor monitoring performance. For all relevant effects
376 in the alpha band, see Table 3.

377

379 *Figure 3.* Task-related power (TRP) in the alpha band (8-12Hz) as a function of process,
 380 position, and creative metacognition. The brain maps in panel A illustrate the interaction
 381 effect of process and position. The diagram in panel B and the brain maps in panel C
 382 illustrate the interaction process, position, and creative metacognition.

383 No further effect involving metacognitive monitoring and creative performance/skill at
 384 at Level 1 or Level 2 was significant for the alpha band. Higher scores in panel C (yellow)
 385 represent higher TRP in the alpha band during idea generation vs. idea evaluation.

386

387 *Table 3. Linear mixed effects models for predicting TRP in the alpha band during creative*
 388 *idea generation and evaluation*

Parameter	Estimate ^a (SE)	β^b	df	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	0.108 (0.017)		15228	6.387	<.001
LEVEL 2					
Monitoring skill (grand mean centered)	-0.011 (0.032)	-.024	96	-0.330	.742
Creative potential (grand mean centered)	0.009 (0.079)	.005	96	0.114	.910
Monitoring skill x creative potential	0.002 (0.148)	.006	96	0.016	.987
LEVEL 1					
Monitoring performance (group mean centered)	-0.001 (0.005)	-.006	15228	-0.113	.910
Creative performance (group mean centered)	-0.006 (0.014)	-.018	15228	-0.405	.686
Temporal/central (vs. frontal)	-0.148 (0.011)	-.475	15228	-13.814	<.001
Parietal/occipital (vs. frontal)	-0.231 (0.011)	-.738	15228	-21.525	<.001

Hemisphere (1 = left, 2 = right)	0.011 (0.011)	.034	15228	1.019	.308
Hemisphere x temporal/central (vs. frontal)	0.053 (0.015)	.170	15228	3.528	<.001
Process (1 = generation, 2 = evaluation)	-0.021 (0.011)	-.067	15228	-1.927	.054
Process x parietal/occipital (vs. frontal)	0.036 (0.015)	.117	15228	2.395	.017

LEVEL 1 x LEVEL 2

Parietal/occipital (vs. frontal) x monitoring skill (Level 2)	-0.060 (0.020)	-.102	15228	-2.976	.003
Parietal/occipital (vs. frontal) x monitoring skill (Level 2) x creative potential (Level 2)	-0.351 (0.093)	-.133	15228	-3.746	<.001
Monitoring skill (Level 2) x creative potential (Level 2) x monitoring performance (Level 1)	0.079 (0.039)	.042	15228	2.005	.045
Process x monitoring skill (Level 2)	-0.054 (0.021)	-.093	15228	-2.636	.008
Process x parietal/occipital (vs. frontal) x monitoring skill (Level 2)	0.071 (0.029)	.120	15228	2.448	.014

Random effects	Proportion of variance	<i>SD</i>	<i>r</i>
Participant (intercept)	36.63%	0.148	
Trial number (slope)	2.48%	0.010	-0.071
Residual	60.89%	0.246	

389 N = 100 with 15516 measurements. Note. The model includes an autoregressive term

390 ($\phi = .11$) and a random intercept (trial number within subject). *Df* = degrees of freedom; *SE*

391 = standard error. ^aEstimates are unstandardized partial regression coefficients. ^b Estimates are
392 standardized partial regression coefficients after z-standardization of all fixed continuous
393 predictors and the criterion (i.e., TRP).

394

395 **3.2.4 Sensitivity analyses in the beta band and theta band**

396 Two analogous analyses with TRP in the theta band (4-8Hz) and the beta band (12-30Hz)
397 were conducted to indicate the sensitivity of alpha band findings. We found most significant
398 effects of metacognitive monitoring and creative performance/skill at Level 1 and Level 2 in
399 the alpha band (see Supplemental Table 1 and Table 2). However, the interaction effect
400 PROCESS x monitoring skills (Level 2) was mirrored in the beta band ($b = -0.026, t(15228) =$
401 $-2.298, p = .022$; see Supplemental Table 1).

402 Furthermore, the additional analyses in the beta and theta band also showed some specific
403 findings. For the beta band, the analysis indicated a significant interaction PROCESS x creative
404 performance (Level 1) and creative potential (Level 2) x creative performance (Level 1; see
405 Supplemental Table 1). For the theta band, the analysis showed a significant interaction
406 PROCESS x creative potential (Level 2) as well as monitoring skills (Level 2) x creative
407 potential (Level 2; see Supplemental Table 2). Since the alpha band was of central interest in
408 this study, we did not further elaborate on these additional band-specific effects.

409

4. Discussion

410 The creative ideation process is characterized by generative and evaluative processes
411 (Benedek and Jauk, 2018; Finke et al., 1996), and we are only beginning to understand brain
412 activation patterns associated with these stages (Kleinmintz et al., 2019). However, to date
413 the accuracy of the evaluative processes has not been considered when studying evaluative
414 and metacognitive functions involved in the creative ideation process (Kleinmintz et al.,
415 2019). By indexing how well people can evaluate the creative quality of their own ideas we

416 were able to explore brain activation patterns during idea generation and idea evaluation,
417 which were associated with creative metacognitive monitoring at the idea and the person
418 level.

419 Specifically, participants with a higher creative potential showed stronger alpha TRP
420 decreases at parietal/occipital brain regions (compared to frontal areas) as metacognitive
421 monitoring skills increased. In line with creativity research, creative potential was related to
422 higher TRP in the alpha band, yet only when monitoring skills were low (Fink and Benedek,
423 2014; Stevens and Zabelina, 2019). Furthermore, participants with higher monitoring skills
424 showed lower TRP at frontal and temporal/central positions during creative idea evaluation
425 compared to idea generation, which argues for reduced cognitive control functions or lower
426 (working) memory load during idea evaluation (vs. generation). This complex pattern of
427 findings was not observed in the beta band nor in the theta band. This indicates some
428 specificity of TRP changes in the alpha band for the creative ideation and evaluation process
429 and its association with performance measures of creative metacognitive monitoring and
430 creative ideation.

431 Although most studies reported the importance of alpha power for the creative idea
432 generation process (Fink and Benedek, 2014; Stevens and Zabelina, 2019), even showing
433 good classification performance (Stevens and Zabelina, 2020), to the best of our knowledge
434 no study to date investigated brain functions during creative idea generation and evaluation
435 by taking the accuracy of the evaluative process into account. Both, the process of idea
436 generation and the process of idea evaluation were associated with pronounced
437 parietal/occipital alpha power decreases, arguing for active visual processing, but creative
438 metacognitive monitoring skills and participants' creative potential moderated this finding.
439 Participants with a higher creative potential and higher monitoring skills (creative and aware)
440 showed stronger parietal/occipital alpha power decreases compared to people with lower

441 monitoring skills (creative but unaware). Since creative metacognitive monitoring skill was
442 independent from creative potential, this neurophysiological finding suggests that people can
443 achieve higher creative performance by means of largely different neurocognitive strategies,
444 associated with parietal/occipital power decreases as creative metacognitive accuracy
445 increases. In line with previous research, this decrease at parietal/occipital sites with
446 increased monitoring skills might argue for reduced internal attention and increased stimulus-
447 dependent visual processing during idea generation and idea evaluation, which might further
448 indicate that these participants put more effort in the partly visual task (Benedek, 2018).
449 However, when monitoring skills were low, creative potential showed the expected positive
450 association with TRP increases at parietal/occipital sites, which is nicely in accordance with
451 creativity literature arguing for increased internal attention and working memory load during
452 creative ideation in order to enable stimulus-independent, self-generative thought processes
453 supporting imagination (Benedek, 2018). This interpretation is further underlined by the
454 interaction between monitoring skills, creative potential, and metacognitive monitoring
455 performance at Level 1. Alpha power increases were most pronounced in more creative
456 people with lower monitoring skills precisely in those trials in which they demonstrated weak
457 monitoring performances. As first evidenced by brain activation, this points to the intricate
458 interaction between creative performance and metacognitive monitoring at an intra- and
459 interindividual level.

460 Since these complex interactions seem to hold for idea generation and evaluation (i.e.,
461 were not moderated by the ideation stage: generation versus evaluation), it could be inferred
462 that cognitive functions related to metacognition play a role in both generation and explicit
463 evaluation processes (Kleinmintz et al., 2019; Lloyd-Cox et al., 2022; Rominger et al., 2018).
464 These cognitive overlaps might be imagination, visualization, mental simulation, and
465 monitoring of potential solutions (see e.g., Christensen and Ball, 2016, for creative

466 evaluation). However, temporal/central alpha power decreased from idea generation to
467 evaluation, which indicates a reduced involvement of associative and memory processes
468 (Luft et al., 2018). Furthermore, decreased frontal alpha power during idea evaluation
469 compared to idea generation was observed in people with higher metacognitive skills. This
470 can be interpreted as reduced cognitive control and lower working memory load during idea
471 evaluation in people showing better metacognitive monitoring skills (Jensen et al., 2002;
472 Klimesch et al., 1999; Rominger et al., 2019a). Therefore, someone might speculate that
473 people with higher monitoring skills might already inherently evaluate and control their
474 creative ideation processes (i.e., cyclic shifts between generation and evaluation; Kleinmintz
475 et al., 2019), which possibly reduces the need for further evaluation and control during an
476 explicit evaluation process.

477 In line with Silvia (2008), we found that people are able to rate the creative value of
478 their ideas (Benedek et al., 2016; Rominger et al., in press; Rominger et al., 2022a). As
479 expected, participants showed good discrimination between more and less creative ideas (Sidi
480 et al., 2020). However, in some contrast to literature, we did not find an association between
481 the creative metacognitive monitoring skills and the creative potential (Guo et al., 2022). This
482 null finding indicates that although creative monitoring shows a specific brain activation
483 pattern during creative ideation, it is not (strongly) associated with the creative potential of a
484 person. However, it should also be noted that the effect sizes for the association between
485 originality and creative metacognitive accuracy are lower for alternate uses tasks compared to
486 other divergent thinking tasks (Guo et al., 2022). Furthermore, our null finding is in some
487 agreement with the study of Urban and Urban (2021), who showed that high creative
488 potential can be observed with and without high creative metacognitive skills. The authors
489 identified three separable groups: One group with high creative potential but no awareness of
490 their potential, a group of participants who were unskilled and unaware, and a group with low

491 creative skills and high awareness. These behavioral findings are in line with the
492 neurocognitive findings of the present study. In our study, those people who showed high
493 creative potential but less metacognitive monitoring skills, exhibited stronger alpha power
494 increases indicating internal attention, higher working memory load, and spontaneous modes
495 of thinking in order to come up with original ideas. Those people, however, who showed
496 better monitoring skills and higher creative potential exhibited parietal/occipital alpha power
497 decreases, indicating stimulus dependent sensory processing and the use of more convergent
498 modes of thinking associated with their monitoring accuracy.

499 This moderating effect of metacognition on brain activation associated with creative
500 potential might suggest at least two routes to creative ideas. This is in accordance with the
501 idea of dual process models of creative thinking (Benedek and Jauk, 2018; Kleinmintz et al.,
502 2019). In these models, both the divergent and convergent modes of thinking are important to
503 finally arrive at a creative and original solution (Benedek and Jauk, 2018). This assumption is
504 further in line with the dual pathway model of creativity assuming the generation of creative
505 output via flexibility and persistence (Dreu et al., 2008; Nijstad et al., 2010). By taking the
506 evaluative accuracy of people into account, this study was able to investigate idea generation
507 and idea evaluation as intimately coupled processes in creative ideation (Fox and Christoff,
508 2014; Kleinmintz et al., 2019). Participants' monitoring and evaluative skills might decide
509 which neurocognitive route is chosen (more dominantly) to come up with a creative output.
510 However, further research is needed to replicate these findings and to investigate if
511 contextual variables such as affect can modulate them (Kaufmann and Vosburg, 2002;
512 Mastria et al., 2019; Mueller et al., 2012; Rominger et al., 2022c).

513 In line with Benedek et al. (2016), we observed higher monitoring skills when
514 subjective ratings (at Level 2) were also high (Ceh et al., 2021). This indicates that people
515 tend to underestimate their creativity (Urban and Urban, 2021), but less so when they show

516 less negative bias and thus give higher ratings (Benedek et al., 2016). The negative
517 association between creative performance and monitoring performance at Level 1 seems to
518 mirror this finding. Given that people systematically underestimate their creative output, it
519 fits that metacognitive accuracy is lower in trials with more original ideas. Nevertheless,
520 further research is needed to determine if and when an association between both performance
521 measures can be observed.

522 **4.1 Limitations**

523 First, the idea generation and idea evaluation phases have a different time duration,
524 which might have weakened the comparability of both phases. Furthermore, both phases
525 included the presentation of visual stimuli, which might have affected the observed brain
526 activation. Therefore, future studies should investigate the stability of the present findings by
527 further parallelizing the assessment of creative idea generation and evaluation as well as by
528 changing the visual information presented during the task.

529 Second, this study specifically focused on the EEG alpha band. Although this
530 constitutes a very first step into the neuroscience of creative metacognitive monitoring,
531 following previous work on creative ideation (Fink and Benedek, 2014; Stevens and
532 Zabelina, 2019), future research should investigate additional sub bands such as beta and
533 theta and their interactions with alpha in more detail. In line with this, we found performance
534 relevant brain activation patterns in the adjacent bands of beta and theta in this study (see
535 Supplemental Table 1 and 2). This hints at the relevance of episodic memory processes (i.e.,
536 theta band synchronization; Klimesch, 1999) as well as top-down processes (i.e., beta
537 synchronization; Fries, 2015) for creative metacognition. Although the applied sensitivity
538 analyses are explorative in nature, and replications are highly warranted to arrive at stronger
539 conclusions, the findings are in accordance with former creativity research indicating a
540 broader range of frequency bands associated with the creative ideation process (see e.g.,

541 Agnoli et al., 2018; Bhattacharya and Petsche, 2005; Boot et al., 2017; Eymann et al., 2022;
542 Jia et al., 2021; Mölle et al., 1999; Rominger et al., 2022b).

543 **4.2 Conclusion**

544 To conclude, the findings of this study provide first insights into the neuroscience of
545 creative metacognitive monitoring, as reflected in the accuracy of evaluative processes in the
546 creative ideation process. In accordance with our assumptions, the alpha band is sensitive for
547 not only creative potential, but also creative monitoring accuracy. The observed interaction
548 effect of creative potential and creative monitoring skills on the observed brain activation
549 pattern is in accordance with the assumption that different people might use different
550 neurocognitive routes to come up with original ideas, depending on their creative monitoring
551 skills. Creative people, which are aware (i.e., higher monitoring skills) showed alpha power
552 decreases at occipital areas, while creative people which are not aware of their creative
553 potential (i.e., lower monitoring skills) showed the expected alpha power increases at these
554 areas. This pattern suggests that metacognitive skills of a person moderate the extend of
555 convergent and divergent thinking processes in creative ideation, consistent with assumptions
556 of dual process models of creative cognition as well as the dual pathway model of creativity.
557 To the best of our knowledge, this study presents first neurophysiological evidence for the
558 involvement of metacognitive processes in creative ideation.

559 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

560 The authors report no conflict of interest.

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